

A CONCEPTUAL REVIEW OF CHITRAK GHRITA**Dr. Rutuja Nazirkar*¹, Dr. Kalyani Jadhav²**¹MD (Scholar) Rasashastra Bhaishajya Kalpana Sumatibhai Shah Ayurved Mahavidyalaya, Hadapsar.²Professor, H.O.D. Rasashastra Bhaishajya Kalpana Sumatibhai Shah Ayurved Mahavidyalaya, Hadapsar.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Rutuja Nazirkar**

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ABSTRACT

Chitrak Ghrita is a effective ayurvedic ghrita for management of Grahani, Pliha roga, Arsha, Agnimandya. This ghrita contains Deepan, Pachana, kaphavatashamaka. Chitrak has carminative and digestive properties, useful in hemorrhoids, and its anti – inflammatory and anti – colic, Chitrak is Ushna, Ruksha, and Grahi in nature According to Vagbhatacharya when Chitrak is administrated with ghee or milk for a month then it acts as Rasayan. It stimulates digestive power, and promoting appetite; it is frequently used in the treatment of a number of diseases specially digestive system.

KEYWORDS: Chitrak Ghrita, Deepana, Pachana.**AIMS AND OBJECTIVE**

To study Chitrak ghrita mentioned in Chakradatta.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda is one of the oldest scientific medical system in the world. Its history of origin started from vedic period.

Bhaishajyakalpana is composed of two words i.e Bheshaj – Medicine

भेषजं औषधरोगनिवारकद्रव्यं। (च सू १/१२६)^[1]

Bheshajya Kalpana – Method or plan of preparation

In this branch there are basically two types of formulations. Primary formulation and Secondary formulation. Primary formulation there are five basic formulations like Swaras, Kalka, Kwatha, Hima, Phanta; known as panchavidha kashay kalpana. Secondary formulation are like Sneha Kalpana, Asavarishta, Avleha, Ksheerapaka, Gutti-Vati, etc.

अथातः स्वरसः कल्कः क्वाथश्च हिमफाण्टकौ ।

जेयाः कषायाः पञ्चैते लघवः स्युर्यथोत्तरम् ॥ १ ॥

(शा.सं.म.ख. १/१)^[2]

Secondary formulation involves Sneha kalpana (Ghrita kalpana)

Sarpi, Taila, Vasa, Majja are type of sneha.

सर्पिस्तैलं वसा मज्जा सर्वस्नेहोत्तमा मताः।

एषु चैवोत्तमं सर्पिः संस्कारस्यानुवर्तनात्॥

(च.सू. १३/१३)^[3]

“Sanskarasya Anuvartanut” – It’s a unique nature of Sarpi

It takes the drug properties into it, without leaving its own inherent properties. It is absorbed in all sukshma strotas of the body.

Modern evidence suggests that ghee- based Ayurvedic formulations have the potential to enhance drug bioavailability and support mucosal healing.

Ghritas are lipid based ayurvedic formulations or medicated ghee, in which ghee is boiled with the decoction or the past of the crude drug, so that the active constituents of drugs get transferred into ghritas.

Chitrak Ghrita is the important formulation which is mentioned in Chakradatta Samhita Grahani Chikitsa Adhyaya.

चित्रकक्वाथकल्काभ्याम् ग्रहणीघ्नम् श्रुतम् हविः।

गुल्म शोथ उदर प्लिहा शूलार्शोघ्नम् प्रदिपनम् ॥

च. द. ग्रहणिप्रकरणं ४/४३^[4]

This same reference is also found in Bruhat Nighantu Ratnakar and Bharat Bhaishajya Ratnakar Volume 2^[5]

MATERIAL AND METHOD

कल्कात् चतुर्गुणीकृत्य घृतं वा तैलमेव वा।

चतुर्गुणे द्रव्ये साध्यंतस्य मात्रा पलोन्मितम् ॥

शा. स. म. खं. ९/१^[6]

1. Kalka dravya – Chitrak Kalka 1 part
2. Sneha dravya - Goghrita 4 part
3. Drava dravya – Chitrak Kwath

In Chitrak Ghrita, Goghrita is taken and heated on Mandagni till it melts then prepared Kalka is added to it. Then kwatha is added and whole contents are boiled together when the water portion get evaporated and Sneha Siddhi Lakshana are obtain.

Sneha Siddhi Lakshana^[7]

1. Varti is formed when Kalka is rolled between thumb and index finger.
2. No crackling sound should be produced when some part of Kalka is put on the fire.
3. Fenodgama in Taila Paka and Phenshanti in Ghrita Paka at the time of completion of preparation.
4. Appearance of Gandha, Varna, Rasa varies from one formulation to formulation.

These all lakshanas are seen when total water is evaporated.

Composition of Chitrak Ghrita

Chitrak

चित्रकोऽनलनामा च पाठी व्यालस्तथोषणः ।

चित्रकः कटुकः पाके वह्निकृत्पाचनो लघुः ॥७०॥

रुक्षोष्णो ग्रहणीकुष्ठशोथार्शः कृमिकासनुत् ।

वातश्लेष्महरो ग्राहीवातार्शः श्लेष्मपित्तहृत् ॥ ७१ ॥

(भा.नि)^[8]

- Botanical Name – *Plumbago Zeylanica Linn*
- Family – Plumbaginaceae
- Vernacular Name

Hindi Name – Cheeta, Chitra, Chitrak, Chita, Chitraka, Chitavur

English Name – Leadwort

Bengali Name – Chita, Chitu

Marathi Name – Chitramul, Chitrak

Gujarati Name – Chitro, Chitra, Pitaro

Telugu Name – Chitramulam, Agnimantha, Tellachitra

Tamil Name – Chittiri, Chittira, Penchitar, Kodivel

Kannada Name – Chitramula, Bilichitramula

Panjabi Name – Chitra

- Synonym

Anala, Dahana, Pithi, Vahnisajanak, Agni, Agnika, Jyothi, Nirdahana, Vanhi, Sikhi, Vyala, Hutasana – all these synonyms denotethe fire. It is because it helps to improve digestion strength. While collecting this herb, usually it is found that the plams get burning sensation due to the hotness of this herb. Hence the synonyms Dahana (burning).

Agnika – “agnitulya ushna sparshe veeryam cha, - Having fire quality

- Varieties

Vagbhata Quoted varieties namely

Shweta (White) – *P. zeylanica*-white;

Peeta (Yellow) &

Asita (Black) Chitraka.

Usually the following varieties are found

For all therapeutic purposes, *Plumbago zeylanica* or the white variety is used.

- Classical categorization :

Sushruta-Pippalyadi, Mustadi, Amalakyadi, Varunadi, Aragvadadi group of herbs.

Vagbhata - Pippalyadi, Mustadi, Varunadi, Argvadadi group of herbs.

Charaka

Deepaneeeya – Group of herbs that improve appetite and digestion strength

Shoola Prashamana – Herbs that relieve abdominal colic pain

Arshoghna – herbs used in treating piles

Lekhaneeya – group of herbs having scraping property.

Bhavaprakasha Nighantu – Haritakyadi varga

Raja Nighantu – Pippyadi varga

- Useful part : Root

- Pharmacological properties :

Rasa : Katu

Guna : Laghu, Ruksha

Veerya : Ushna

Vipak : Katu

Doshghnata : Kaphagnha, Vatashamak, Pittakar

Karma : Deepan, Pachan, Ruchikar

- Indications - Gulma, Adhmana, Atisara, Grahani, Krumi, Chardi, Kushta, Visha, Jwara

चित्रकमुलम् दिपनीयपाचनियगुदशोथ अर्थः शूलहराणाम्।

च. सू. २५/४०

SNEHA DRAVYA

Goghrita

घृतं पित्तनिलहरं रसशुक्रौजसां हितं

निर्वापणं मृदुकरं स्वरवर्णप्रसदनम् ॥

(च. सू. १३)^[9]

In Shatapatha Brahmana three words are used as an alternative word for Goghrita namely Aajya, Ghrita and Sarpi. Similarly, 4 different words are denoted to Ghrita in Aatreya Brahmana as is Navanita, Aajya, Ghrita and Aayuta which tells that Ghrita was used since the vedic period.

Ghrita is obtained animal kingdom like cow, goat, sheep, buffalo, camel, etc. out of these cows ghee (Go Ghrita) is consideredas the top and best choice among Sneha Dravyas. Ayurveda discriminates their particular feature and recommends the GoGhrita (cow's ghee) as the choice for both food and medicinal purposes.

सर्पिस्तैलं वसा मज्जा सर्वस्त्रेहोत्तमा मताः ।

एषु चैवोत्तमं सर्पिः संस्कारस्यानुवर्तनात् । १३ ।

(च.सु. १३/१३)^[10]

Ghrita (Clarified butter), Tail (of sesame), Vasa (muscle fat), and Majja (bone marrow) are considered the best Sneha. Among these Ghrita is superior as it possesses

the qualities of Samskara i.e. blending with other substances having different properties or Gunas without losing its own properties or Gunas.

Synonyms – Avi, Sarpi, Aajya

Samskar is addition of new properties and Anuvartana means its acceptance by the host. Goghrita doesn't shed off its properties such as Snigdha, Sheeta, etc. rather it carries its own properties also it carries the properties of the ingredient by which it is processed.

- Sushrutacharya has mention that properties of Ghrita are said to enhance as the duration of it increasesd. It is termed as “Purana Ghrita”

According to different Acharyas the period varies.

10 yrs old Ghrita is Purana.

11-100 yrs old Ghrita is Kumbhaghrita.

100 yrs old Ghrita is Mahaghrita.

Vernacular Names

Hindi : Ghee

English : Ghee / Clarified butter

Marathi : Tupa

Sanskrit : Ghrita

Properties of Go Ghrita :-

Rasa - Madhura

Guna – Guru, Snigdha, Sara

Virya – Sheeta

Vipaka – Madhura

Doshagnata – Tridosahara

Karma – Medhya, Balya, Vayasthapana, Ayushya,

Rakshoghna,

Rasayana, Chaksushya, Vishapaha

DISCUSSION

Chitrak Ghrita is one of the unique Ghrita preparation mentioned in Chakradatta Samhita with very less and easily available ingredients. This Ghrita indicated in Grahani, Arsha, Angnimandya, Pliha roga.

Mode of action on Grahani and Angnimandya.

Nidana (Etiological factors)

Dysfunction of Grahani

Loss of Structural & Functional Integrity Of Grahani

Grahani & Agnimandya Manifestation

Agnimandya, Arsha, Grahani etc. these are the common diseases in clinical practice. According to Ayurveda, main cause of disease is dosha prakopa. Agnimandya contribute significantly towards the disease pathogenesis. It is root cause of Amadosha and it is crucial factor for manifestation of most of the diseases including Grahani, Arsha. In short, Doshaprakop, Mandagni are the most important factor in causation of diseases. Therefore, drug used for treatment should act directly or indirectly on Agni. In such a condition, Chitrak Ghrita play important role because Chitrak is Deepana, Pachana, Ruchikar, Arshoghna, Shoola Prashamana, Grahi properties. The action of chitrak is Jawarahara, Kushthagana, Swasahara, Shulahara, Kandughna.

CONCLUSION

Chitrak Ghrita is a classical Ayurvedic formulation this reference available in Chakradatta Samhita in Grahani Chikitsa Adhyaya. Grahani is the common diseases in clinical practice, and main cause of disease is Agnimandya, Doshaprakopa. Agnimandya and Doshaprakopa contribute significantly towards the disease pathogenesis, So, Drug used in treatment should act on Agni. In such a condition, Chitrak Play important role because it possesses Deepana, Pachana and Grahi properties.

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